

THE ESSENCE OF FORMING ECOLOGICAL EDUCATION IN CHILDREN

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Abstract: This article discusses the content and essence of forming environmental education in students.

Key words: Educational system, methodology, environmental education, nature conservation.

The main tasks and goals of environmental education are to make people interested in nature and the realities that occur in it, to determine the causes of problems between people and nature, to find ways to solve them, and to have sufficient environmental knowledge. implementation of environmental protection. The tasks of ecological education are as follows:

1. development laws of society and nature; in-depth training of relations between them and preparation of a person who can think modernly;
2. to prepare a generation that knows the ecological condition of various natural areas and prepares an ecological plan for the future in the direction of socio-economic planning and production forces;
3. every person, society and various groups, categories, classes within the society, the nature in which they live, raising young people who serve to preserve its resources;
4. To explain to the members of the society the beauty of the place where they live, valleys, hills, mountains, their importance for human life and health in the development of their social, cultural, religious views and traditions.

In the implementation of the above tasks, kindergarten teachers, school and educational students, through various games and movies, connect natural and social sciences to the natural reality and ecological conditions in the place where they live. should carry out educational work and attend classes.

When such things are done, every kindergarten child, schoolchild and student will not be indifferent to the withering of a plant, the inability of a bird to fly, the burning of a hill or forest, and the useless flow of water. He feels sorry for nature, its creatures, the water he drinks, and a sense of inner desire to improve the situation arises. This is a new biological force in man. The revolution of his new intelligence will be the victory of ecological education.

On the basis of ecological education, people and members of society should behave correctly and rationally in the preservation and economical use of nature and its resources, devote practical work to solving environmental problems, environmental education, upbringing and culture of the individual. didn't care

The nature of ecological education. Republic of Uzbekistan

Many decisions issued by the management envisage the expansion and improvement of work related to nature protection and the training of experts in this field to the level that meets the requirements of scientific and technical development. The solution to these problems is to raise the socio-economic development of our country to a new level, to preserve our mother nature, which is a part of the universe, to use its natural resources in a planned and economical manner, living beings; including clean air, water and soil for humans, as well as plant and animal habitats.

2. Purpose and tasks of environmental education. The main tasks and goals of ecological education are to make people interested in nature and the realities that occur in it, to determine the causes of problems between people and nature, to find solutions and measures, while having sufficient ecological knowledge. implementation of environmental protection. The tasks of ecological education are as follows:

1. development laws of society and nature; in-depth training of relations between them and preparation of a person who can think modernly;
2. socio-economic planning and production forces who knows the ecological condition of different natural areas and preparing a generation that will create an ecological plan for the future;
3. each person, society and different groups, categories within society, the nature in which the classes themselves live, the cultivation of young people who serve to preserve its wealth;
4. their social, cultural, religious views and

To carry out the work of explaining the beauty of the living place, valleys, hills, mountains, their importance in human life and health in the development of traditions

3. Directions of environmental education. One of the main directions of ecology education in our republic is to organize continuous environmental education on the conservation of nature, economical use of its various resources, and to conduct general education in this field among employees and managers of various enterprises, starting from kindergarten.

1. In order to strengthen and properly implement the environmental education related to nature protection, it is necessary to conduct pedagogical experiments and observations, as well as to create educational textbooks, to train sufficiently highly educated specialists;

2. It is necessary to continuously carry out ecological education among different groups of the population everywhere, to instill in students love for nature, to improve their skills, to cultivate young people as ecological economists in terms of preserving and saving natural resources;

3. Short and long-term programs to educate children about the environment in terms of learning the reality, protecting the environment, creating endurance, tolerance, and tolerance skills for environmental education and education in kindergarten and school children. It is necessary to organize annual courses;

4. Carrying out ecological education in educational institutions. Ecological ways of conducting education in kindergartens and schools. Starting from carrying out activities related to the preservation of nature, its beauty and natural resources among families, kindergarten children and schoolchildren, to teach the young and growing generation to love the environment, its plants, animals, water and soil. it is necessary to raise them as compassionate, nurturing and enriching souls.

1. In order to achieve these goals, it is necessary to educate kindergarten children on the basis of special programs such as "Methodology of ecological education and upbringing", "Getting to know nature" and to inculcate the elements of environmental education related to nature into the minds of children with the help of various games;

2. To instill love for nature in children special methodological manuals, recommendations, "World around us", "Nature around us", "Natural science" etc. in simple, simple and understandable forms based on educational and game materials should be conducted;

3. Provides environmental education to children educators and Methodists themselves have completed special courses, they must be experienced specialists;

4. On the basis of the "Ecological education and nature style" program, it is necessary to organize retraining courses for educators, lectures, experience sharing seminars, and increase the knowledge, levels, and working abilities of employees.

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